

Smarandache's Concurrent Lines Theorem by Mircea Eugen Şelariu

Let's consider a polygon (which has at least four sides) circumscribed to a circle, and D the set of its diagonals and the lines joining the points of contact of two non-adjacent sides. Then D contains at least three concurrent lines.